

IMPROVING ENGLISH SKILLS BY CHOOSING BEST MOTIVATION IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO DEAF CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

In this article is given effective ways of teaching English to children with disabilities. Also Author gives their attention to Motivation. There is given lots of different types of theoretical and practical motivations.

Nowadays most people want to learn English language. Because, this language is spreading very largely all of the world. So if this language should be easier to occupy, more and more people can learn it without difficulties. There is given effective methods for teaching and learning English. It makes easier to learn language.

Best way of teaching English is giving motivation. Motivating children each group before they start teaching English will have a positive effect on the future lesson.

Requirements for motivation:

To arouse interest in learning English for children;

Spiritual preparation for future challenges;

Increasing the love for life and live;

The main purpose of learning foreign languages is to have full understanding of the purpose.

Motivation methods can be used as follows:

- Motivational video, audio (they should be in English then in Uzbek);

- Providing pupils with detailed information about the benefits of learning English and experts from their peers who can speak English freely;

- to encourage them to read and understand the next most popular fiction books written in English, or to give them the opportunity to comprehend and understand the most popular British songs.

In this method, pupils will have idea of the possibilities provided by this language, even if they do not understand English sentences, and identify the main objectives of their study. When the main objective is defined, there is desire to learn this language.

At the next level, they should have the skills. There is a wealth of data on both positive and negative behavioral skills in psychology [2]. The language experience may impede or facilitate a newly acquired phenomenon. In order to facilitate the same language experience, it is best to use words that are easy to understand during the first lessons, words and rules that are close to the mother tongue. The language units studied are classified into two major and

easy categories, from the methodological point of view. Easy units include the commonality (similarity) of linguistic phenomena in the language experience of students [3]. For example, an international foreign language vocabulary may be displayed with words in the mother tongue or in a second language: tennis-tennis, dollar-dollar, business -business. Grammatical fronts are also easy enough to find. If we account the pupils of learning English who are blind, we should use the methods which are audio lingual method (by speaker, by the lecture), “ Total physical response method (to learn language by movements and sounds), we know blind pupils can write and read by Brille alphabets. So it is useful for them to learn English by Grammar translation method (to learn English by grammatical ways, do exercise belongs to grammar rules). Audio lingual method - in this method for using to learn by heart new vocabularies and rules of pronunciation. Also it is important for listening and speaking. Because, after pupils listen some new topics, they have some information about this. As a result, their listening skills improve. In working with children who has disabilities, create English atmosphere. Vocabulary is one of the main idea skills of English. Because without vocabulary learners cannot speak, listen, write or use grammar. According to psychologists, human beings learn the life experiences by words, because thoughts are made by words. Word is a central unit of a language: language first of all is the system of words without of sufficient vocabulary. Students cannot communicate effectively and express ideas. Having a limited vocabulary is also a barrier that prevents students from learning a foreign language. If learners do not know how to expand their vocabulary, they gradually lose interest in learning. In this theme most methodists made lots of work. They are E. Antony, J. C. Richards, Th. S. Rodgers and others. Especially E. Antony identified three levels of conceptualization and organization, which he named approach, method and technique. According to his model: approach is the level at which assumptions and beliefs about language and language learning are specified; method is the level at which theory is put into practice and at which choices are made about particular skills to be taught, the content to be taught, and the order in which the content will be presented; technique is a level at which classroom procedures are described..

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